

In Search of Identities: How Chinese Economic Immigrants Invest in their English Language Learning and Use

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates how three Chinese economic immigrants' identity construction is influenced by their acculturating experiences in Australia and how the process of their identity construction mediates their investment in English learning/use and cross-cultural practices. The study employs multi-case study research and narrative enquiry as merged methodologies drawing on a semi-structured interview with each participant. Thematic analysis reveals that while they exerted agency to strike a balance between the host culture and their heritage culture, they seemed to strongly identify with their heritage culture, namely as Chinese, rather than hyphenating or hybridising their identity. In addition, the Chinese immigrants' investment in English language and cross-cultural practices seemed to be mediated by their perceptions of the interplay between capital and their different identities, including their Chinese identity. The findings have significant theoretical, pedagogical, and policy implications.

Keywords: Chinese immigrants, identity, investment, second language learning, Australia

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INTRODUCTION

Despite the Australian government's advocacy for multilingualism and support for the teaching and study of community languages, English remains the country's predominant language and the primary medium of communication, which seems necessary as its multicultural society is characterised by diverse languages and cultures partly due to immigration. English proficiency, therefore, plays an essential role in immigrants' ability to access education, employment, healthcare, and social services, as well as successful social integration. Immigrants' English ability is also in the best interest of the country to sustain social cohesion and economic development (McDonald et al., 2019).

Chinese-born residents are the third largest group of overseas-born living in Australia, accounting for 2.5% of the total population (ABS, 2023), yet according to the 2021 Census, people who spoke Chinese languages at home represented the largest proportion of the population with low English proficiency (ABS, 2022). Thus, it is of theoretical and practical importance to understand the extent to which Chinese immigrants are able to engage in and commit to English learning/use, Australian social interaction and community practices.

The current study aims to unravel the complex individual and social factors influencing Chinese economic immigrants' language and cultural learning as they integrate into their host society, by employing the notions of identity and investment constructed by Norton and her colleagues (Darvin & Norton, 2015; Norton, 2013; Norton & De Costa, 2018). The study's findings may provide insights for Australia's future language policy as well as Australia's settlement services, e.g., the Adult Migrant English Program (AMEP) (see DHA, 2024a).

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents theories related to identity and investment, and provides a comprehensive overview of existing research, identifying key themes, gaps, and methodological approaches that inform and justify the direction and significance of the current study.

Identity

From a poststructuralist perspective, identities are socioculturally constructed ongoing narratives, which develop and evolve across time and space (Block, 2015).

An individual's identity is dynamic, evolving and multilayered rather than stable, fixed and unitary (Norton, 1997), which is constructed and reconstructed through his or her engagement within specific communities of practice in the social world (Block, 2015). Besides, while the process of identity construction involves self-ascription and self-positioning by individuals, they are simultaneously positioned and recognised in particular ways by other participants in interactions (Block, 2015).

Norton (2013) defines identity as "the way a person understands his or her relationship to the world, how that relationship is constructed across time and space, and how the person understands possibilities for the future" (p. 4). For second language (L2) learners, language learning is a kind of identity work (DFG, 2016), and language and identity are inextricably interconnected since "identity constructs and is constructed by language" (Norton, 1997, p. 419). As regards international migrants, their identities do not simply involve adding the new to the old or a half-and-half combination (Block, 2007), which instead should be viewed as hybrid and being constantly produced and reproduced anew (Hall, 1994).

Investment

Investment can be defined as "the commitment to the goals, practices, and identities that constitute the learning process and that are continually negotiated in different relations of power" (Darvin, 2019, p. 245). The notion of investment views learners as having a complex identity that changes across time and space and is transformed through social interactions (Norton, 2013). Individuals' investment involves not only affirming their existing identities and empowering them to claim the right to speak, but also affording them the ability to imagine new identities and affiliations (Norton, 2013). Furthermore, learners invest in a language because they anticipate acquiring a wider range of symbolic and material resources, which will, in turn, enhance the value of their cultural capital and social power (Norton, 2013).

Research on acculturation and identity of Chinese immigrants

Several researchers interested in immigrants' acculturation and identity have targeted Chinese economic immigrants in a context where they navigate between their mother/heritage language and language of the host country and negotiate between their heritage culture and the host culture.

Primarily drawing on narrative data, this line of research has revealed that while integrating into mainstream society, many Chinese immigrants tend to develop a hyphenated, in-between identity (Fang & Huang, 2020; Liu, 2015) and that their identity construction is an ever-evolving, non-linear process (Amireault, 2020; Fang & Huang, 2020; Huang et al., 2021; Liu, 2015). Chinese immigrants are found to identify themselves differently from each other, and in terms of identity performance, they tend to enact their identities differently in different contexts through either their language use or behaviour (Fang & Huang, 2020; Huang et al., 2021; Liu, 2015; Paciocco, 2021), which points to the complexity and intricacy of their sense of self.

Another remarkable theme emerging from previous studies is that, while Chinese immigrants recognise the importance of enhancing proficiency in their host society's official/dominant language (Amireault, 2020; Han, 2012), they find that no matter how well they spoke that language and how closely they acted like Anglophones, they would still be categorised as the Other in a predominantly white country because of their physical appearance (Fang & Huang, 2020; Liu, 2015), which indicates that identity negotiation is embedded in a power hierarchy.

While these studies provide valuable angles to researching Chinese immigrants' identity construction, only Liu (2015) and Huang et al. (2021) were conducted in Australia. In addition, neither of these two studies purposefully explored how the participants' role as language learners interact with their identity construction. Nor was the impact of identity construction on the immigrants' language investment examined. Thus, the present study aims to address this gap in the literature.

Research on Chinese-background learners' language investment

Many studies investigating Chinese English as a second language (ESL) learners' identity and investment in language and culture learning have been centred on students in school or study-abroad (SA) university settings in societies where English is either the official or dominant language. For example, Lee (2008) and Arkoudis and Love (2008) investigated how imagined identities and imagined communities could influence Chinese-background students' investment in English learning, English oral participation and social interaction. Those two studies also indicate that, a language learner's motivation for learning English may not translate into investment in the language practices of a given context if, for example, they are positioned as "inadequate, incapable, or unworthy" (Darvin

2019, p. 245) or the practices do not engage the learner's hopes and desires for the future.

Scholars have adopted the construct of capital in Darvin and Norton's (2015) investment model in their inquiry by drawing on case study methods. It was found that Chinese ESL learners selectively invested in identities that were likely to transform their lives (Cao & Newton, 2019; Chang, 2016; Crowther, 2020; Shi & Guo, 2021; Sung, 2019). Together, these studies have deepened our understanding of Chinese ESL learners' investment by revealing the complex interrelationships between their investment in learning, their existing and imagined identities, cultural and social capital, and ideology, as well as how the interplay between identity, capital, and ideology mediates their desire and commitment to learning.

However, in this line of research, little is known about the language and cultural investment of Chinese immigrants, who, as they integrate with their receiving society, have different experiences from Chinese-background students who study at an English-medium educational institution. Thus, the current study aims to explore this under-researched area.

Research questions

This study aims to shed light on the complex, dynamic, and situated processes of identity construction of Chinese immigrants in Australia, and also how these processes are related with their investment in language learning/use and cultural practices. The following research questions have been formulated to guide the study:

1. What are Chinese economic immigrants' perceptions about the impacts of acculturating experiences in an Australian society on their identity construction?
2. How does their identity construction influence their level of investment in English language and cross-cultural practices?

RESEARCH METHODS

Case study and narrative enquiry

The current study employs a narrative enquiry methodology embedded in a multi-case research design (Sonday et al., 2020). It draws on the three participants' storytelling experiences to develop an in-depth description and analysis of them as three comparative cases.

A case study is suitable for the present study as it has been playing a burgeoning role in research focusing on learner subjectivity, identity, ideologies, and narratives of learner experience (Duff, 2020), having led to new understandings as regards "what it means to be a language learner, speaker, or transnational citizen in the 21st century" (Duff, 2014, p. 250). For example, case studies exploring the ideologies and identities of immigrants and transnational migrants have highlighted the indeterminacy of their language learning experiences and life pathways, and the constraints and affordances associated with their language learning and social engagement (Duff, 2014). The study employs a multiple-case approach because we can better understand a single-case finding by looking at a range of similar or contrasting cases (Miles et al., 2014). Besides, the inclusion of multiple cases can enhance the "precision, validity, stability, and trustworthiness" (Miles et al., 2014, p. 33) as well as the "external validity or generalisability" (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016, p. 40) of our findings.

Also, narrative enquiry is well suited to the present study because narratives of migration are beneficial to understand how people cope with personal and social changes in the processes of "uprooting" and settlement (De Fina & Baynham, 2012, p. 3). In addition, oral narrative creates a space for immigrant voices and so is significant in the expression of identities. Another reason why narrative enquiry is suitable for the present study is that, as Barkhuizen et al. (2014) suggest, it can be a valuable tool to shed light on the inner mental worlds of language learners and how they organise their experiences and identities and represent them to themselves and to others.

Participants

The current study aims to shed light on the complexity, intricacies, and particularity of immigrants' perceptions of their identity and investment through "fine-grained analysis" (Baker & Edwards, 2012, p. 18), rather than for maximum generalisation and representativeness. An "idiographic" rather than "nomothetic

approach” (p. 30) was, accordingly, adopted in sampling. The study sought maximum diversity among the cases and selected participants who were likely to reveal different narratives (Duff, 2020). Eligible participants for the current study needed to be Chinese economic immigrants in Australia over 18 years of age. Three immigrants in total were selected and participated in a semi-structured one-to-one interview. Figure 1 shows the profile of these three participants, highlighting distinctive differences among them, and they are further described as follows.

Figure 1. *Profile of the participants*

Pseudonym	Yang	Li	Chen
Age group	35-40	50-55	20-25
Gender	F	F	F
Locality of origin	North China	East China	South China
Year first in Australia/Visa type	2007/Student	2007 or 2008/Travel	2007 or 2008/Travel
Year of immigration/Visa type	2016/Business	2010/Skilled	2013/Child
Educational background	Master’s degree	Bachelor’s degree	Undergraduate student
Occupation	Mandarin teacher	Small business owner	University student

Yang was a part-time Mandarin teacher and a mother of three. She first came to Australia in 2007 to study for her master’s degree, after which she went back to China and lived there for several years. She moved back to Australia in 2016 on a business visa and obtained permanent residency two years later.

Li was a small business owner who immigrated to Australia on an employer-sponsored visa. She first came to Australia in 2007/2008 on holiday, by which time

some of her relatives had already settled there. She then sent her teenage son to Australia for education and decided to immigrate here in 2010.

Chen was a 1.25-generation immigrant (Rumbaut, 2004) who came to Australia with her parents in her adolescent years. After she arrived, she completed an English language course for young second language learners before going to secondary school. As a university student studying health sciences, she also worked part-time at a dental clinic.

Data collection

The current study gathered narrative stories from three participants through semi-structured interviews in which they talked about their perceptions and lived experiences of identity construction and investment in language and cultural practices. The interview guide (see Appendix A) consists of a list of mostly open-ended questions formulated by translating the research questions into colloquial language to generate spontaneous and rich descriptions from the interviewees (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2018). The open-ended questions focused on the participants' subjective experiences (Seidman, 2013) and gave them an active role in narrating their stories about acculturating, identity construction, and investment. All interviews were conducted in Mandarin, the participants' native language, to facilitate naturally constructed narratives and conversations without linguistic barriers (Huang et al., 2021) and thus to augment the richness of information obtained.

Data analysis

Thematic analysis was employed to analyse interview transcriptions. Coding was conducted following a theoretical approach, the process driven more by the research questions than by the data themselves (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Twenty provisional, descriptive codes were established as suggested by the study's theoretical framework and research questions, previous research findings, and pilot interviews (Saldaña, 2016). The prefigured codes were then revised, fine-tuned, deleted, and expanded to include additional codes emerging during the analysis (Creswell & Poth, 2018). During this process, an intercoder agreement assessment was conducted to enhance the reliability of the analysis (Saldaña, 2016).

After all data extracts had been coded, a list of 19 descriptive codes was finalised (see Appendix B), which were subsequently classified into three candidate themes.

After that, a thematic map was created to show the relationship between codes and individual themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The themes were then reviewed and refined by revisiting the coded data extracts and by considering the validity of individual themes and the thematic map in relation to the entire data set (Barkhuizen et al., 2014). Finally, a detailed, systematic analysis was conducted and written for each individual theme by organising related data extracts into a coherent and internally consistent account (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

FINDINGS

Research Question 1 (What are Chinese economic immigrants' perceptions about the impacts of acculturating experiences in an Australian society on their identity construction?)

To answer this question, the three participants' identity construction across time are delineated case by case, and similarities and differences among them are also discussed.

Yang's acculturation and identity construction

Overall, as Yang navigated between her native culture and Australian culture, her Chinese identity became increasingly stable, while her imagined identity as a "true Australian" was replaced by a mother of three bicultural, bilingual children. In addition, her identity performance included both her Chineseness and her status as an Australian resident. Yang's identity construction process is described in more detail below.

Despite the uneasiness when she first came to Australia in 2007, Yang actively tried to interact with the "locals" and devoted herself to "getting immersed in the Australian way of life". By so doing, she hoped not only to improve her English but also to integrate with "true Australians", a community in her imagination (Kanno & Norton, 2003).

However, in this process of integrating, she gradually felt like an outsider to the Australian culture. For instance, she could not understand people's jokes and Australian advertisements. Conversely, if she did not speak Chinese or keep in contact with her Chinese peers, her emotional needs wouldn't be satisfied. The prolonged contact with the English language and Australian culture seemed to cause the destabilisation of Yang's sense of self (Block, 2007), which made her

uncomfortable. Thus, “failing” to become a member of the Australian society, or “one of them” in her own words, she decided to return to China after completing her studies in 2009:

But as I found it difficult to assimilate after trying, I chose to go back to China after graduation. At least I had a sense of belonging in China because it is my homeland. I found it difficult to regard Australia as my home country because there were too many things that I couldn't understand.

The left side of Figure 2 symbolises Yang's identity construction during the above-described period. The pink oval represents Yang's Chinese identity, and the green oval on the left stands for her imagined identity of a “true Australian.” The dotted line connecting those two ovals represents Yang's ambivalence and struggle as she navigated two cultures and two identities, which she experienced again after she moved to Australia permanently in 2016.

Figure 2 *Yang's identity construction*

This time, as a new immigrant, Yang initially still attempted to assimilate into the “locals” so that they would accept her as a “true Australian”. However, as she felt

“miserable and depressed” because of the problems associated with her English abilities and her identity ambivalence, she decided to reconcile herself to the fact that she could not and did not have to assimilate. The right side of Figure 2 depicts Yang’s identity construction since this reconciliation.

The red oval still stands for her Chinese identity, and the larger overlapping orange oval portrays her dual embodied identity in social interactions. She identified herself as a Chinese living in a “foreign land” who represented China and embodied her identity as a strong, good-mannered Chinese woman who, as a “good citizen”, obeyed the law and respected the culture of Australia. She reflected that she had a stronger sense of belonging to the “diverse and multicultural” Australian society than before, especially after obtaining her permanent residency.

Moreover, describing her three children, one 1.75-generation (Rumbaut, 2004) and two-second generations, as being both Australian and Chinese, and anticipating them to be more likely to speak English better than Mandarin in the future, Yang had begun to visualise her future role as a mother of three bicultural bilinguals. The dotted line between the green oval and the pink oval signifies the possible impact of her newly imagined identity on her self-identification and her acculturating process.

Li’s acculturation and identity construction

While content with her life in Australia, Li had never been ambivalent about her Chinese identity and strongly identified herself as Chinese rather than Australian or Australian Chinese. Taking an eclectic approach to acculturation, she tended to perform her identity ethnically and culturally as a Chinese who was also an Australian citizen.

Figure 3 illustrates Li’s identity construction. One of the main differences between Li and Yang was that, before Li permanently moved to Australia, the Australian society was already an imagined community (Kanno & Norton, 2003) for her, where some of her relatives had already settled and her son was attending high school. Thus, her acculturating process (represented by the dotted line connecting the red oval and the green oval in Figure 3) started before immigration through studying English, learning about Australian culture, and her visits to Australia.

Figure 3 *Li's identity construction*

The right side of Figure 3 depicts Li's identity construction after immigration, as she gradually learned more about the culture of Australia while adjusting to her new life. Whereas she endorsed many aspects of the host culture, there were some institutions and norms that she could not understand or was unwilling to accept. As regards Chinese culture, she viewed it as a collective enterprise for "us", i.e., all Chinese people, to preserve the "beautiful" traditional customs and norms.

Similar to the other two participants, Li tended to use the personal pronouns "we" and "our" when talking about Chinese culture while using "they" and "their" when describing her perceptions of Australian culture. For Chinese speakers, these pronouns are "makers of collectivity that includes or excludes the speaker or the writer, respectively" (Huang et al., 2021, p. 4). By using these linguistic forms, she seemed to index Australians to the non-self-group and the Chinese to the self-group (Huang et al., 2021).

Accordingly, Li asserted that she had a stronger sense of belonging to Chinese than Australian culture. She explained that her cultural identity was reflected in every aspect of her life, including adhering to Chinese cuisine, making friends with fellow

Chinese immigrants, and maintaining ethnic traditions. Despite having resided in Australia for over 10 years, Li emphasised that she had lived in China for much longer, and thus Chinese culture had influenced the formulation of her values and beliefs more significantly.

Therefore, similar to Yang, Li firmly identified herself as Chinese (the red oval in Figure 3) who consistently enacted a well-mannered, well-bred, and respectful Chinese woman living in Australia (the larger orange oval). She added that she had never felt uncertain about her cultural identity: “I think it is unnecessary to think about this. I’ve never feared that my identity will tilt or change.” In other words, different from Yang, while adapting herself to the host culture, Li did not experience a period of struggle due to the destabilisation of one’s sense of self (Block, 2007).

Another difference between Li and Yang was that Li did not explicitly describe an imagined identity for her future in Australia. However, she did envisage her moving back and forth between China and Australia regularly, just like what she had been doing, once the travel restrictions due to COVID-19 were eased, which would enable her to continue both the maintenance of her heritage culture and the acquisition of the dominant culture. Such ability to traverse global spaces with speed and ease was likely to continue affording her great agency and creativity in negotiating her sense of self and enabling her to maintain her strong Chinese identity despite living in Australia (McEntee-Atalianis, 2019).

Chen’s acculturation and identity construction

Although in her adolescent years, Chen experienced ambivalence between her Chinese identity and her imagined identity as Australian, as she grew up, she gradually felt comfortable solely being Chinese while enacting various identities in different contexts. In addition, as a young adult, she started imagining new possibilities for her future.

Figure 4 illustrates Chen’s identity construction. Similar to Yang, Chen also experienced ambivalence and struggle surrounding her identity (represented by the dotted line on the left) as she integrated into Australian society. Having been used to focusing on language structures and linguistic details in English learning, Chen was relatively weak in English fluency and real-life communication when she first came to Australia in 2013 and thus dreaded talking with the “locals”. The government-provided English course did not help much as she “kept talking in Chinese with other learners from China”.

Figure 4 *Chen's identity construction*

Chen's English problems and the differences between Chinese and Australian cultures made her secondary school years a "miserable experience". She found it difficult to be responsible for her studies as she had been used to being guided and pushed by teachers. As there were few international students in the secondary school, Chen "had to" mix with the "local" students. The cultural differences emerging from such experiences seemed to strengthen her attachment to and identification with her heritage culture (the pink oval in Figure 4) and weaken her desire for membership in her once-imagined community - the "Australian locals" (the green oval on the left):

I found that there was little I could talk about with them. We watched different shows. We listened to different music... I was like: "I don't belong here at all", feeling that I don't belong to Australia but to China.

There were many elements in Australian culture that Chen endorsed and was willing to incorporate into her originally established cultural system, such as respect for multiculturalism and various religious beliefs. However, despite living in Australia for almost ten years, Chen thought she still had a stronger sense of

belonging to Chinese culture. She was proud that she could play a traditional Chinese instrument and was delighted to interact with Gweilo (a Cantonese slang term for Westerners), who showed interest in Chinese culture.

Chen preferred to define herself as Chinese rather than Australian, or Australian Chinese (represented by the pink oval), and she viewed her Chinese identity as a marker of her membership to a group of people of the same ancestry/ethnicity residing in this “foreign country”, which she thought was important for her psychological wellbeing. To her, Australia was just where she lived and where her acculturating process was an ongoing one, partially driven by her desire to thrive in this “foreign country”. With such a desire, Chen had imagined new possibilities for the future, aspiring to become a registered dentist after obtaining her bachelor’s degree (the green oval on the right side).

Chen’s identity performance (the orange oval in Figure 4) differed from that of Yang and Li. It seemed that Chen self-consciously presented different aspects of herself, and spoke and acted differently when being with people who were not Chinese:

I can’t just be myself when I am with people from other countries because they don’t know or understand my culture. So, I need to behave more internationally... When interacting with foreigners, I feel like I am in a different mode.

While individuals may identify themselves with a specific social group, they might simultaneously project their selves differently across time and space through various semiotic means (Block, 2007). On a specific occasion, a person may linguistically and non-linguistically perform an identity that is “socially salient” (Paltridge, 2012, p. 24). Thus, in such contexts, Chen might wish to be recognised by her interlocutors as an Australian resident or a global citizen, thereby a member of the multicultural Australian society. Chen’s context-dependent identity strategy was not favoured by Yang and Li, both of whom claimed to consistently enact a Chinese identity irrelevant of context:

I want people to see that my characteristics coordinate with my cultural background. I don’t want people to see me as a banana (yellow on the outside, white on the inside) who has Chinese physical characteristics but does things that Gweilo do. (Yang)

Research Question 2 (How does their identity construction influence their level of investment in English language and cross-cultural practices?)

The three participants' levels of investment were analysed through their existing and imagined identities across time, which emerge from their above-illustrated narratives about their past, present, and future. Four themes emerged from such analysis: (1) investment in erstwhile imagined identities, (2) investment in existing identities, (3) investment in newly-imagined identities, and (4) the role of capital. Each will be presented as follows.

Investment in erstwhile imagined identities

In the case of their past imagined identities, these visualised possibilities had a positive impact on the participants' investment in language learning and practice. For instance, before officially immigrating to Australia, Li had asked help from an English tutor with grammar rules, expecting that there would be linguistic challenges for her, a new immigrant, in her erstwhile imagined community - the Australian society. Similarly, as Yang had hoped to blend in with the "locals" and striven for membership in this imagined community, she had been highly invested in English learning and use and "getting immersed in the Australian way of life". For example, she did a part-time job to practise her English; she would go to a footie game; and she would go camping with her "local" friends and attend their parties to have conversations.

Investment in existing identities

The participants' strong Chinese identity clearly translated into their commitment to Chinese language use and cultural practice. At the same time, they all more or less understood the necessity of English learning and use due to their identity as Australian residents.

On the one hand, after their imagined identities had become existing identities, or their aspiration to the imagined communities had been relinquished (in Yang and Chen's case), the participants' ever-present, solid Chinese cultural identity played the most important role in their investment. For example, Chen mentioned that she preferred to speak Chinese and socialise with people of Chinese ethnicity and to work with Asian students for group assignments. In addition, while she celebrated Australian festivals just for fun, she celebrated Chinese festivals because she felt culturally connected to them. In a similar vein, Li lived in a neighbourhood where

there are many “Huaren” (people of Chinese ethnicity), and so spoke Chinese and mixed with “Huaren” most of the time.

On the other hand, however, as they were all cognizant of and valued their Australian resident/citizen identity, they never dismissed the importance of the investment in English learning/practice and Australian social practices. For example, as mentioned earlier, Yang had a stronger sense of belonging to Australian society after obtaining her permanent residency. Accordingly, despite that she preferred to mix with her Chinese peers rather than blend in with “foreigners”, she was fairly invested in her identity as an Australian resident:

I also tell my children that since we have immigrated to Australia and live in this society, we should get involved in it. We should make a contribution to the country and play a role in this society. (Yang)

As the only adult in the family who spoke English, she played the role of the liaison between her family and society, responsible for everything that kept the home running in this English-speaking country (e.g., calling the local council, communicating with Centrelink and Medicare, filling out forms for her children at different clubs, etc.), which she thought had strengthened her overall English communicative abilities.

Investment in newly-imagined identities

As mentioned in the previous section, both Yang and Chen had formed new possibilities for their future. Accordingly, their investment was also influenced by their new imagined identities - an Australian registered dentist in Chen’s case. This imagined identity motivated her to invest in her studies and in her part-time job at the dental clinic, which involved not only daily communication in English but also academic English writing and the learning of terminology related to medicine, dentistry, and health care. For Yang, her aforementioned imagined future self as a mother of three bicultural bilinguals had also made her put more investment in English learning/use and Australian cultural practices:

I hope that by celebrating Australian holidays, my children can integrate into Australian culture... I talk with my son in English when he learns how to do the stuff (micro:bit)... I have to improve English if I want to keep up with them. And if I, as their mother, can’t understand them when they want to talk to me about something important, they will be sad. (Yang)

The role of capital

The influences of the participants' identities on their investment in English learning/use and cultural practices can also be analysed with reference to the construct of capital (Darvin & Norton, 2015). As Norton (2013) argues, individuals invest in language learning and related cultural practices if they expect to acquire a wider range of symbolic resources and material resources, which will, in turn, increase the value of their cultural capital and social power. In the interviews, the three participants concurred that English proficiency was essential for academic success, career advancement, social interactions, and thus better quality of life in Australia:

If you don't speak English, you won't be able to have a good quality of life. If your English is not good, you should learn and try to improve it. No one will hire you if you cannot communicate with customers. (Yang)

English is definitely very important. It can make things more convenient for you and make people who you talk to more comfortable... You have to use the language on various occasions in all aspects of your life, including your work. (Li)

Thus, Li had invested in English learning before immigrating to Australia, hoping that English, as a form of symbolic resource, would strengthen her social power. Similarly, Yang was highly invested in English learning and use while doing her master's degree as, through this, she hoped to acquire a wider range of symbolic resources, including educational credentials and friendships. As regards Chen, her aforementioned investment in her imagined identity of an Australian registered dentist might be related to her expectation that the new identity would afford her a wider range of symbolic resources (social and professional networks) and material resources (income) which would, in turn, raise her social power.

Meanwhile, the three participants admitted they had not devoted enough time to English learning. Based on their answers, they seemed more invested in Chinese use and community practices. The reason might lie in their perception that engaging in English learning and social practices was not likely to enhance the value of their existing cultural capital and social power to a substantial degree, or in other words, to improve their quality of life significantly. In contrast, for example, Yang and Li seemed to anticipate higher returns on investment in their Chineseness, as both Li and Yang's family and most of their friends were Chinese and they both had business relations in China.

In conclusion, the participants' selective investment in language learning/use and cultural/social practices had been mediated by their identity, a site of struggle between existing and imagined identities (Darvin, 2019). Moreover, they seemed to either invest in their existing identities in the hope that they would acquire more symbolic and material resources or invest in accessing more symbolic and material resources, enabling them to claim more powerful identities than they imagined.

DISCUSSION

The current findings regarding the three Chinese immigrants' acculturation and identity construction support the poststructuralist perspective on identity, which states that an individual's identity is dynamic, evolving, and multilayered and is constructed and reconstructed through his/her participation in particular communities of practice.

Specifically, whereas the three Chinese immigrants all seemed to have constructed a form of biculturalism featuring coexistence and harmony, this biculturalism did not result in a hyphenated, blended, or hybrid cultural identity in them. Although they embraced their Australian residency or citizenship, they attached significant importance to their Chineseness for feelings of continuity and emotional well-being.

While the current study has not identified the in-between (Liu, 2015) or hybrid (Amireault, 2020; Fang & Huang, 2020) self-identification reported in previous studies, the two first-generation immigrant participants' solid Chinese identity is also evident among some first generations in Amireault (2020), Huang et al. (2021), and Liu (2015). As researchers have noted, first-generation immigrants tend to bring with them significant attachments to their home culture when they relocate to their receiving country (Liu, 2015), and their Chinese self-identification correlates highly with their personal affective ties and contributes significantly to their feelings of continuity (Huang et al., 2021). In comparison, 1.5- and second-generation immigrants are more likely to be immersed in the culture of the host society (Liu, 2015) and thus are more likely to develop a form of melange and flexibility (Fang & Huang, 2020) in their often bicultural identity. That could explain why the 1.5-generation immigrant participant (Chen) in this study tended to perform different identities according to different contexts even though she defined herself as Chinese, the same as the other two participants.

The study's findings regarding the three participants' investment in their English language ability and cross-cultural practices show that investment can be mediated by the interplay between the learner's complex, multifaceted, evolving identities, imagined possibilities for the future, and anticipated increase in cultural capital and social power.

The three economic immigrants seemed to show an ambivalent attitude, and the level of such investment seemed to fluctuate across time and space. On the one hand, their commitment to English learning/use and their Australian-associated identities reflected their perception that such identities were likely to enable them to acquire a broader range of symbolic and material resources, which would, in turn, increase the value of their cultural capital and social power. This mentality is shared by the student participants in a few previous studies, for example, Chang (2016), Shi and Guo (2021), and Sung (2019). On the other hand, the three participants seemed to be highly invested in their solid Chinese identity and Chinese cultural and community practices to affirm their identity or in the expectation of accessing greater material and symbolic resources.

The current study differs from previous studies focusing on Chinese background students in English-medium educational settings. Participants in those studies were usually student sojourners, who, as temporary migrants, might be more motivated to invest in their study than in acculturating and prefer to remain separated from the host culture for higher life satisfaction and better academic adjustment (Anderson & Guan, 2018). That is probably why acculturating-associated identity construction was infrequently explored in this line of empirical enquiry. As findings of the current study show, navigating different cultures and identities, Chinese immigrants might choose to selectively invest in both their native language and the dominant language and in both their heritage culture and the host culture, probably to earn the maximum return.

IMPLICATIONS

The findings of the study reveal that whilst Chinese economic immigrants may engage in striking a balance between their heritage culture and the host culture, they, as voluntary immigrants, might not necessarily develop an in-between or hybrid identity. Also, the current study has shown that the model of investment, in particular, the theorisations of investment, identity, and capital (Darvin & Norton, 2015), can be powerful tools to investigate Chinese immigrants' commitment to English learning/use and cross-cultural practices.

In regard to pedagogical implications, it seems important for teachers in English tuition programmes for immigrants, such as the Adult Migrant English Program (DHA, 2024a), to consider how to facilitate Chinese immigrant students' Australian identity construction and thereby, their sense of affective connections to and ownership of the English language. Activities such as "Drawing an Australian", for example, might serve to guide learners to take a critical view of the often taken-for-granted depictions of "Australians" (Sumithran, 2021, p. 70).

Meanwhile, considering some Chinese immigrants' high level of investment in Chinese language and cultural practices, it might be a good idea to try including their first language or discussing their heritage culture in teaching activities. However, caution must be taken to avoid the exoticisation of learners' cultural backgrounds (Norton, 2013) or accentuating cultural differences, which could create an environment of cultural otherness (Lee, 2015). Further, educators might also need to consider aligning their pedagogy with Chinese immigrant students' other identity categories and imagined identities, which could provide the impetus for their investment in English learning and speaking (Darvin, 2019).

Lastly, concerning language policy, given that English, or standard English, is represented as the national and de facto official language of Australia under different guises (Lo Bianco & Slaughter, 2017) and that only cultural diversity rather than linguistic diversity is recognised, respected and celebrated (Scarino, 2014), immigrants and migrants who are native speakers of the "outside", foreign, or community languages (Lo Bianco & Slaughter, 2017, p. 451) such as Mandarin Chinese are likely to suffer from linguistic subordination which could lead to linguistic inferiority complexes resulting in self-marginalisation, low sense of social belonging, and thus limited investment in English language and cultural practices in the dominant society.

In addition, as revealed in the findings, immigrants might feel unmotivated to invest in further English improvement after attaining their permanent legal status. Thus, it is worth considering whether the English-level requirements for visa applicants and the English-only citizenship test are beneficial or meaningful for immigrants in the long term (Kunnan, 2022) regarding, for example, employment and social participation.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Despite the significant findings of the study, a few limitations should be mentioned. One main limitation is that, due to the relatively short time frame of the investigation, the study has relied on only one data source, namely the participants' oral narratives. Including other sources would have provided thicker descriptions and enhanced the research validity. Another shortcoming is that the study has been unable to purposefully recruit more participants who might "represent the widest possible range of the characteristics of interest" (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016, p. 98) and thus provide greater diversity. The small scale means that findings are not generalisable to all Chinese economic immigrants in Australia in light of their cultural, language, and social class differences.

Based on the above limitations of this study, possible avenues for future research are suggested as follows. One valuable area for subsequent investigations is giving sufficient consideration for intersectionality (Block & Corona, 2014), namely analysing the complex confluence of often overlapping and interdependent identity categories besides ethnicity, such as gender, religion, and class (Norton & De Costa, 2018). Greater diversity across study subjects could also be achieved by including Chinese immigrants with unique life trajectories and acculturating experiences in Australia, such as those who used to be holiday working makers (DHA, 2024b). Another direction for other scholars is expanding the time frame to utilise other research instruments and techniques, such as written reflections and observations, and to include interview data from participants' families and friends for triangulation (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). In addition, a longitudinal study would be suitable for gaining a deeper and more nuanced understanding of immigrants' dynamic, ever-evolving identity construction process and their complex attitudes towards investment at different times.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Despite being preliminary and having limitations, it is hoped that the current study has helped advance our knowledge about the complexity and diversity of how people may construct their identities and invest in learning the official language in a new host country. Understanding this issue will help us understand the significant reasons and factors underlying people's attitudes, behaviours and acculturation processes in a new country they migrate to, thereby allowing us to support them when appropriate to promote social harmony and understanding.

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APPENDIX A: INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Questions for RQ1 (What are Chinese economic immigrants' perceptions about the impacts of acculturating experiences in an Australian society on their identity construction?):

1. What were your perceptions of Australian culture before you came here?
2. What are your perceptions of Chinese culture?
3. Have your views on Australian culture and Chinese culture changed since you moved here? How?
4. Would you say you have a stronger sense of belonging to Chinese culture or to Australian culture? (Or would you say you feel belonging to both or neither?)

5. How would you define yourself today? Would you say you are Chinese, Australian, Australian Chinese, or Chinese Australian?
6. How important is your Chinese identity to the sense of who you are in Australia? (Can you elaborate?)
7. Would you say your identity has changed since you came to Australia? (Looking back now, how has the process of integrating into the Australian society influenced your identity? Has the learning/usage of English and living in Australia affected your identities? How?)
8. Has anyone around you or any of your family or friends back in China pointed out any difference in your identity? (What have they said? What do you think of the differences?)
9. Do you think you show different aspects of yourself in different contexts? (Are they influenced by other people's expectations? How important are these different aspects in relation to each other? Which are more or less important?)

Questions for RQ2 (How does their identity construction influence their level of investment in English language and cross-cultural practices?):

1. Have you taken any English courses since you came to Australia? Why? Have you learned/practised English in other ways? Why?
2. In the language classroom and on other occasions, what makes you speak more when interacting with others in English? When do you feel reluctant to interact with others in English?
3. On what occasions do you prefer/tend to speak/use Chinese and in what contexts do you prefer/tend to speak/use English? (Do you ever switch back and forth between the two languages? Why?) (In general, do you use English more or Chinese more in your daily life?)
4. Have you made new friends in Australia? How did you meet them?
5. In general, do you have more Chinese- or English-speaking friends in Australia? Why? What do you do with them?

6. What holidays and festivals do you celebrate? Why?

APPENDIX B CODING SCHEME

Category			Code	Abbreviation	Definition
Acculturating	Perceptions of Australian/Western culture	1	Foreign, "they", "their"	AC-F	Participants view Australian/Western culture as foreign, "theirs".
		2	Endorse, willing to accept/incorporate	AC-WTA	Participants endorse and are willing to accept the institutions, norms, values, attitudes, etc. in Australian/Western culture.
		3	(Tried but) not willing to accept but respect	AC-R	Participants are not willing to accept but respect the institutions, norms, values, attitudes, etc. in Australian/Western culture.
	Perceptions of Chinese culture	4	Native, "we", "our"	CC-N	Participants view Chinese culture as native, "ours".
		5	Emotional bonds, attachment, pride	CC-E	Chinese culture is connected with participant's emotions, attachment, and pride.
		6	Embedded in identity, wishing to maintain	CC-I	Participants find Chinese culture embedded in their identity and wish to retain it.
	Cultural sense of belonging	7	Stronger sense of belonging to Chinese culture	CSB-CC	Participants have a stronger sense of belonging to Chinese culture.
		8	Stronger sense of belonging to Australian culture	CSB-AC	Participant has a stronger sense of belonging to Australian culture.
		9	Equal sense of belonging to both cultures (in-between)	CSB-CC&AC	Participants feel that they belong to both Chinese and Australian cultures simultaneously.
Identity construction	10	Self-ascribed identity	I-SA	Participants' definition of themselves - Chinese, Australian or Chinese Australian/Australian Chinese.	
	11	Other-recognised identity	I-OR	Participants' identity in others' eyes; how he/she is positioned by others.	
	12	Identity performance	I-P	How the participant performs/embodies different identities in different contexts.	
	13	Identity negotiation, ambivalence, struggle	I-N	How participants negotiate their identity while adapting to their life in Australia (and any experience of ambivalence and struggle along with the negotiation).	
	14	Imagined identity/community	I-II	Participant's imagined identities/communities at different times.	
Investment in language learning/use and cultural practices	15	Selective investment	IN-SI	How the participants choose to invest in English learning/use or cultural practices depends on the specific context.	
	16	Investment in existing identity - Chineseness	IN-EI-C	A situation where participants invest in his/her existing identity (Chinese side).	
	17	Investment in existing identity - Australianness	IN-EI-A	A situation where participants invest in their existing identity (Australian side).	
	18	Investment in imagined identity	IN-II	A situation where participants invest in their imagined identity.	
	19	Capital	IN-C	A situation where participants invest in English learning/use or cultural practices expecting to gain valuable material and symbolic resources.	